

Measuring the contribution of BIP/ZIP in achieving Sustainable Development Goals in Lisbon: A Data-Driven Evaluation

Secondment Research Report

Researcher: Androniki Pappa

Partner organisation: Lisbon City Council

Place(s): Lisbon

Start date: 1 March 2022

End date: 31 June 2022

Date of report: 24 July 2022

Status: Draft

RE-DWELL "Delivering affordable and sustainable housing in Europe" has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956082

The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Abstract

This report was produced during a four-month secondment at Lisbon City Council as part of the MSCA-ITN RE-DWELL programme. The research aims to assess the contribution of the BIP/ZIP participatory funding programme to the achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the city of Lisbon. Combining qualitative document analysis, thematic SDG mapping, and a preliminary data-driven evaluation methodology, the study identifies key linkages between BIP/ZIP objectives and localized sustainability targets. It proposes a dashboard-based assessment tool and self-assessment recommendations for future participatory projects.

Disclaimer:

This report reflects the views and analysis of the author, Androniki Pappa, a PhD researcher at ISCTE-IUL. The content has not been formally reviewed or endorsed by Lisbon City Council and does not represent its official position.

Contents

Abstract.....	1
Contents	2
I. Plan of Activities	3
II. Introduction.....	4
III. Methodology	5
1. Sustainable Development Goals and BIP/ZIP.....	8
1.0 The BIP/ZIP Program	8
1.1 Global View: Sustainable Development Goals – researcher's assessment.....	8
1.2 Urban and Local View: Localisation of SDGs and ODS Local	12
1.3 Specific View: BIP/ZIP Objectives and SDGs.....	16
1.4 Comparative Results.....	27
2. Data driven Evaluation of BIP/ZIP	29
Methodology	29
3. Self – assessment	32
Recommendations	32
References.....	33
Annex 1 – Relevance of SDS for BIP/ZIP and identification of themes – Researcher's assessment.....	34
Annex 2 - SDGs that apply to the context of Lisbon and identification of themes - Based on ODSLocal	46
Annex 3 - Themes per SDG	49

I. Plan of Activities

Table 1. Performed activities and outputs in relation to the adapted plan of activities in Table 1.

Planned Activity No	Phase	Performed Activities	Outputs
1	Identification of indicators and metrics for sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review of literature on sustainability International agendas and reports for sustainability (global) Localisation of Sustainable Development Goals & International case studies that develop sustainability indicators at a local level. (urban) Sustainability in the Portuguese and Lisbon context (local) Strategies and metrics of sustainability and participatory budgets (specific) Evaluation of participatory projects Evaluation of BIP/ZIP: indicators and metrics; application stage and post-evaluation 	(O1) Index of targets and themes for sustainability from the global to the local
2	Understanding BIP/ZIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review of BIP/ZIP's key documents and secondary data existing in the Municipality's datasets Mapping of the SDG targets to the BIP/ZIP Goals 	(O2) Index of BIP/ZIP objectives and correlation to sustainability goals and targets and identification of emerging themes
3	Data-driven analysis of BIP/ZIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualitative research and data collection Raw data collection and Qualitative coding of the BIP/ZIP projects' activities for the composition of a dataset that will serve as the basis for data analysis 	(O3) Composition of dataset with information on project name, year, location, partners, funding, status, activities and sustainability themes
4	Identifying gaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analysis of O1 and O2 for: Correlation of sustainability targets in the examined scales to draw conclusions on the integration of participatory budgets and BIP/ZIP in the official monitoring of the SDGs in Lisbon 	(O4) Comparative analysis of global, local and specific
5	Analysing and visualising the sustainability of BIP/ZIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experimentation on analysis and visualisation tools: geolocated maps (Rhino-Grasshopper, QGIS), semantic analysis (Gephi), data analysis (Orange, Excel) Drawing Key Outputs	(O5) Preliminary analysis and visualisations (O6) Methodological Recommendations
6	Introducing a computer aided methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaboration with computational researchers for developing a computationally aided evaluation methodology 	(O7) Dashboard creation: Data analysis and visualization (O8) Conference Paper (Sigradi 2022)
7	Writing Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measuring the impact of BIP/ZIP in the SDGs in Lisbon Delivery and showcasing of data analysis dashboard Self-assessment Recommendations 	(O9) Research Report & Presentation to the Municipality

II. Introduction

Participatory and co-governance in urban regeneration have been increasingly integrated in local development strategies globally, as tools to achieve social and territorial cohesion with a great focus on disadvantaged neighbourhoods and populations. This rise is also significantly associated with the implementation of international directives for sustainability, such as the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (United Nations General Assembly, 2020) with the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), to which national and local authorities commit and which consider participatory urbanism as key for the achievement of the sustainability targets.

In this context and focusing on participatory urbanism, cities on the one hand update their local development strategies to implement the agreed goals and targets, and on the other hand develop roadmaps and indicators to monitor their progress towards these goals.

This research focuses on the participatory funding of the BIP/ZIP Program in Lisbon and aims to measure the contribution of this program towards the achievement of the SDGs for the city of Lisbon. This report presents a preliminary study conducted during the secondment period from March to June 2022.

Sustainable Development and participatory funding

The United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was approved in 2015 by all 193 member states of the United Nations and contains 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs), formulated within five pillars: people, planet, prosperity, peace and partnership. The goals are set out in 169 targets.

Cities are the breeding grounds for social, political, economic and cultural activities and therefore play a crucial role in the overall success to attain the SDGs. Municipalities worldwide develop their own mechanisms to implement and monitor their contribution towards sustainable development, producing context specific methodologies, such as strategies for sustainable local development and localised metrics.

Participatory budgeting and other forms of participatory urbanism are seen as accelerators for achieving the SDGs at a local level, due to the collaborative ways of urban governance they introduce, and their efficiency in tackling cross-disciplinary challenges, such as inclusivity and inequalities (UN-Habitat, 2020). Indeed, participatory urbanism is a key element of the UN Agenda 2030, as it is being linked to multiple goals and targets, such as the target 16.7 that is dedicated to actions that “ensure responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making at all levels” (Annex of the 2030 Agenda, 2017).

The report ‘Exploring the Role of Participatory Budgeting in Accelerating the SDGs: A Multidimensional Approach in Escobedo, Mexico’, published by the UN-Habitat (2020) showcases good worldwide cases of participatory budgeting and their contribution to achieving the SDGs and further identifies specific targets that are linked directly to participatory budgeting. These are: 4.7; 5.b; 6.2; 7.1; 10.2; 11.3; 11.7; 16.6; and 16.7.

Looking at the case of the BIP/ZIP Program in Lisbon and its evolution throughout its 11 years of life, we are able to find multiple targets that relate to the implemented projects.

III. Methodology

This report presents a preliminary methodology for the data-driven evaluation of the BIP/ZIP Program, based on the triangulation of three elements, as seen in fig. 1: 1. Sustainable Development Goals and BIP/ZIP 2. Data-Driven evaluation of BIP/ZIP; and 3. Self-assessment.

At the first level, the analysis of the Sustainable Development Goals generates knowledge on sustainability themes that are useful both for the data-driven evaluation of BIP/ZIP and for the self-assessment.

At the next level, the results of the self-assessment provides input for the data-driven evaluation of BIP/ZIP which consequently informs the conceptualisation of sustainable development goals and targets at a local level.

fig. 1 Methodological overview

According to this triangulation, the methodology presented in fig. 2 is organised in 3 sections: 1. Sustainable Development Goals and BIP/ZIP 2. Data-Driven evaluation of BIP/ZIP; and 3. Recommendations for self-assessment.

Section 1 is approached through 5 steps:

- First, document review of BIP/ZIP to understand the Program's focus, such as the definition of the priority areas through the social, economic and urban characteristics, the main aims and areas.
- Secondly, a review of the Sustainable Development Goals and targets and their relevance to BIP/ZIP: *very relevant; relevant; not relevant; relevant at the strategy level*. This contributes to an understanding of the potential contribution of BIP/ZIP to achieving SDGs in Lisbon. Additionally, this analysis provides general themes **(g)** that relate to the BIP/ZIP Program.
- Thirdly, research on literature and cases studies for the localisation of SDGs, provides methodological input for the recontextualization process, as well as offers urban themes **(u)** in relation to the second step.
- Fourthly, the focus on the context of Lisbon through the ODS Local initiative is formative of localised themes **(l)**, as well as helps to identify targets that are relevant for Lisbon and reversely, themes that are relevant according to the second step of the study but are not yet covered by the ODS Local.
- Finally, the review of the BIP/ZIP documents to construct an index of the Program's objectives and focus over time. Furthermore, the correlation of each objective to specific SDGs and targets, based on a combined index of (g), (u) and (l). This step is supplemented by the identification of additional themes for the recontextualization of the SGDs for BIP/ZIP.

At this point, the evaluation should include the results of a self-assessment of the BIP/ZIP individual projects conducted by the partners of each program and based on the implemented activities. Recommendations for this step are covered in Section 3.

Section 2 is approached through 4 steps.

- The second section introduces the conceptualisation of a data-driven, evidence-based evaluation of participatory models. Each project is treated as a data point in the dataset with all the relevant attributes associated to it. To this, the first step refers to the *data collection and cleaning*, to compose datasets for analysis. The data are manually collected through: the annual successful applications published at the website of Bip/Zip <https://bipzip.cm-lisboa.pt/>; the website of ForumUrbano <https://forumurbano.pt/>; the documents shared by the CML with the researcher.
- Secondly, the manual mapping of attributes through a qualitative coding process (Saldaña, 2021) to enrich the datasets.
- Thirdly, multiple methods of data analysis are tested to select appropriate methods and visualisations that resulted in the definition of a necessity to reduce the complexity of data through data clustering methods. For this step of the methodology the researcher collaborated with computational experts.

- Finally, the results are tested and visualised in Interactive Dashboards that are capable to preliminarily show the potentials of a data-driven methodology and provide visual correlations among the clusters off projects.

Section 3 is the composition of a set of recommendations for self-assessment based on the localised SDG themes of Section 1, to provide data to be imported in the dashboard of Section 2.

fig. 2 Methodology diagram. Source:author.

1. Sustainable Development Goals and BIP/ZIP

1.0 The BIP/ZIP Program

For the understanding of the core of the BIP/ZIP Program several documents were studied. The most fundamental for this research are:

- “CARTA DOS BIP/ZIP Bairros e Zonas de Intervenção Prioritária de Lisboa”, (CML, 2010) to understand the definition of the priority areas through the social, economic and urban characteristics;
- “Fichas caracterizacao bipzip – 67 areas”, to understand the conditions per area
- “PROGRAMA BIP/ZIP LISBOA 20-- PARCERIAS LOCAIS CRITÉRIOS DE AVALIAÇÃO E PONTUAÇÃO DAS CANDIDATURAS” (CML, 2011-2022), to understand the evaluation criteria
- “Ciclo e regras do programa BIP/ZIP Lisboa 20-- - parcerias locais”(CML, 2011- 2020)

Additional sources:

- “Mudar a política de habitação em Lisboa” (Roseta, 2013); “Dos pecados urbanos à energia bip-zip” (Roseta, 2015); “An integrated toolbox for deprived neighbourhoods | URBACT”(An integrated toolbox for deprived neighbourhoods | URBACT, 2021); “Good Practice Summary – Lisbon Local Development Strategy for Neighborhoods or Areas of Priority Intervention (BIP/ZIP): an integrated toolbox” (CML and DMHDL, 2017).

1.1 Global View: Sustainable Development Goals – researcher’s assessment

The first assessment refers to identification of goals and targets that can relate to the local context and the BIP/ZIP Program. At this stage, the targets are not linked to specific objectives nor projects of the BIP/ZIP Program, but they are simply assessed by the researcher and colour-coded according to the categories: ‘very relevant’; ‘relevant’; ‘not relevant’; ‘relevant at the policy level’. The detailed table can be found in Annex 1 – Relevance of SDS for BIP/ZIP and identification of themes – Researcher’s assessment.

Results

The assessment of the SDGs and targets is visualised in graphs that are illustrative of the explored relationship. Analysing only the ‘relevant’ and ‘very relevant’ targets in fig. 3, this first assessment shows that the BIP/ZIP Program is very related to the goals 16, 4, 8, 11, 5, 4, 3, 1 and 2. At a second level, it has some or little connections to the goals 12, 9, 10, 15, 17 and no connections or almost no connections to the goals 6, 7, 13 and 14. Furthermore, seven indicators from the goals 16, 17, 12 are relevant to the BIP/ZIP Policy but are less likely to be translated to a project-based evaluation.

Additionally, looking at fig. 4, there is an outstanding number of indicators that show little connection to the BIP/ZIP in the goal 17, followed by a relatively little connection to targets of the goals 14, 15 and 10.

Further to the absolute numbers of targets per SDG, it is necessary to visualise the relative relation between BIP/ZIP and the targets. This is important, as the number of targets per indicator is not steady and therefore the percentage of BIP/ZIP’s ‘very relevant’, ‘relevant’ and ‘relevant at the policy level’ and indicators within each goal denotes the level to which BIP/ZIP could potentially correspond to each one of the goals. These relationships are depicted in the series of diagrams in fig. 5.

fig. 3 Source: author's analysis

fig. 4 Source: author's analysis

fig. 5 Relative relations of BIP/ZIP to targets per SDG. (Source: author's analysis)

Finally, a visualisation of BIP/ZIP as a ratio of SDGs in fig. 6 can be conceptualised as a definition of the Program from the perspective of sustainable development.

fig. 6 BIP/ZIP as SDGs. (Source: author's analysis)

1.2 Urban and Local View: Localisation of SDGs and ODS Local

Localisation Literature

This step is conducted after literature on localising the SDGs. Key References as a methodology as well as sources of themes are:

- *Local Indicators for the 2030 Agenda (Sustainable Development Goals)* (Van Herck et al., 2019)
- *Measuring sustainable development goals at a local level: A case of a Metropolitan Area in Romania.* (Nagy et al., 2018)
- *Indicators for European cities to assess and monitor the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).* (Maio et al., 2020)
- *Building Urban Datasets for the SDGs.* (Siragusa et al., 2021).
- *European Handbook for SDG Voluntary Local Reviews.* (Siragusa et al., n.d.).

Additional Sources:

- *Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals in cities* (URBANET, n.d.)
- *Making the Sustainable Development Goals work for local communities everywhere* | by Daniel Christian Wahl | Medium. (n.d.).

Recontextualisation

As in other international cases for localisation of the SDGs, monitoring the progress of SDGs at the local level of Lisbon Municipality requires a recontextualization. Van Herck, Vanoeteren, and Janssen (2019) in their analysis of the Flemish context highlight four criteria for the recontextualization:

1. **Relevance for local authorities**(Van Herck, Vanoeteren and Janssen, 2019): Some sub-goals cannot link to proposed indicators as they are directly aimed at the global South.
2. **Level of impact of the local authority:** Some goals are a matter of national or federal level and the municipal level cannot have control over them.
3. **Availability of data**
4. **Link with local indicators**

Methodologically, this research is following a theme-based process to contextualise the SDGs for BIP/ZIP, at least at this point of research. This process is seen in other cases, such as the Flemish context in *fig. 7*, which introduce thematics, rather than specific indicators for monitoring.

Theme	SDG 1	SDG 2	SDG 3	SDG 4	SDG 5	SDG 6	SDG 7	SDG 8	SDG 9	SDG 10	SDG 11	SDG 12	SDG 13	SDG 14	SDG 15	SDG 16	SDG 17
Poverty	X	X	X	X		X	X	X		X	X						
Childcare	X			X													
Residential care (e.g. Home care, Residential care centre, Local service centre, Elderly care)	X	X	X		X					X	X						
Housing	X					X	X		X	X	X	X	X				
Local food strategy		X										X					
Health	X	X	X			X		X			X						
Integration and diversity				X	X			X		X	X						X
Leisure (youth, sport and culture)			X							X	X						
Education	X			X				X									
Energy	X		X				X		X		X	X					
Water						X							X				
Environment and nature management		X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X		
Waste policy								X			X	X		X			
Spatial planning						X			X		X		X		X		
Work and economy		X		X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X				
Mobility			X						X		X	X					
Safety			X	X							X						X
Local global policy				X				X		X		X					X
GIS (geographical information systems)						X				X			X				
Procurement policy								X				X					
Civil affairs											X						X
Public Governance					X					X							X
Human resources policy			X	X	X			X		X	X						X
Finances	Finance is an essential part of every SDG. A number of indicators refer specifically to budget, namely SDG 8, 10, 11 and 17.																
Participation	Participation is part of every SDG. A number of indicators refer specifically to participation, namely in SDG 3, 10, 11 and 16.																
Service	Core task of local government. SDG 16 has a number of specific indicators relating to services.																

fig. 7 Linking Policy-themes to the SDGs. Source: (Van Herck, Vanoeteren and Janssen, 2019, p. 15)

ODS-Local

Portugal has developed its own process to monitor SDGs, providing information at a municipal level. For this purpose, the ODSLocal initiative (*ODSlocal*, no date), has been developed by the National Council for Environment and Sustainable Development (CNADS), ICS-ULisboa Observatory (OBSERVA), Centro de Ciências do Mar e do Ambiente (MARE) and 2adapt to mobilise municipalities and relevant stakeholders to achieve the SDGs at a local level.

For the 169 targets outlined by the Global Indicator Framework, the ODS Local has identified 109 indicators that apply in the context of Lisbon. These are collected and presented in Annex 2 - SDGs that apply to the context of Lisbon and identification of themes - Based on ODSLocal.

Results

fig. 8 and fig. 9 show the distribution of localised indicators per SDG and target for Lisbon according to the ODS Local and fig. 10 illustrates a definition of Lisbon through SDGs, based on the ODS Local.

Localised indicators per SDG for Lisbon Municipal area

fig. 8 Diagram by the author based on information by the ODS local (5/4/2022)

Localised indicators per target for Lisbon Municipal area

fig. 9 Diagram by the author based on information by the ODS local (5/4/2022)

Stemming from Van Herck, Vanoeteren, and Janssen (2019) analysis, the identified indicators are shaped by the available data. Hence, figures 8 and 9 alone are not necessarily representative of the relevance of each of the targets for the local context of Lisbon, albeit they are representative of the available data to measure the respective targets.

For instance, target 8 is focusing on indicators that measure foreign visitors to museums, declared income, employment rate, unemployment benefits, gender income disparity, salary, banks and ATMs. However, the target could as well relate to local economic growth, local business and alternative economies that are more difficult to map and measure.

Localised indicators per SDG for Lisbon Municipal area

fig. 10 The definition of Lisbon through SDGs, based on the ODS Local. (Source:author).

1.3 Specific View: BIP/ZIP Objectives and SDGs

The first assessment of BIP/ZIP in the context of SDGs, allowed for some first conclusions on the character and potential contribution of BIP/ZIP in accelerating the achievement of the SDGs.

In this last step, the study presents a detailed mapping of the BIP/ZIP themes and objectives that stems from an aggregated study of the annual documents "Ciclo e Regras" (CML, 2011-2020). The table presents data for the editions 2016-2022, as before 2016 there was no information on specific themes and objectives. The mapped objectives are linked to specific goals and targets, based on the extracted themes

Mapping Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to BIPZIP Themes

BIPZIP Theme	Project Objectives	BIP/ZIP edition	Direct/Indirect relation to SDGs	Targets	Emerging themes	Notes on objectives
Improve Neighborhood Life	- improving the image of the neighbourhood, by residents and society, from the visual aspect to overcoming social prejudices	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019, 2018, 2017, 2016		8.9 11.1; 11.4 10	- neighbourhood image - social prejudice	
	- the promotion of the sense of belonging and co-responsibility and preservation of the common heritage , through recreational, cultural and environmental activities	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019*, 2018*, 2017*, 2016*		11.4; 11.3; 11.7 10.2 4.7 16.7	- sense of belonging - common heritage	* in versions 2019-2016 the environmental aspect is missing
	- the development of sports and leisure activities, favouring neighbourhood and/or inter-neighbourhood cohesion	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019, 2018, 2017, 2016		11.3 11.4 11.a 4.7 3.4 16.7	-cohesion through sports and leisure	
	- the promotion of support and community solidarity initiatives;	2022, 2021		11.3; 11.5; 11.2 16.1; 16.2; 16.10 10.3 1.2; 1.4; 1.5 4.7	-solidarity initiatives	
	- the promotion of initiatives that contribute to safer neighbourhoods;	2022		11.7; 11.1; 11.2 10.7 16.1 3.4; 3.8	-safety	
- the promotion of sustainable neighbourhoods and communities	2022		11; 11.2 2.4 3.6 4.7 8.8 9.1 12.6 1.5	-sustainable neighbourhoods and communities		
Competencies and Entrepreneurship OR Competencies for active citizenship	- the empowerment of various vulnerable groups, in order to help solve problems and develop good personal and community practices;	2022, 2020, 2019, 2018, 2017, 2016		1.5; 1.b; 1.3; 1.4; 2.1; 2.2 4.7 5.b 8.5; 8.3 9.c 10.3	-empowerment of vulnerable	
	- life-long training and professional adaptation and retraining, especially for groups most excluded from the labor market	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019		4.1; 4.3; 4.4; 4.6; 4.7 8.5 2.3 5.1 10.3	- training -professional adaptation -training of excluded	

	- the promotion of the local economy , privileging the social and solidary economy , as well as economic activities and job creation	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019, 2018*, 2017*, 2016*		2.4; 2.3 12.5 8.3; 8.9 9.1; 9.3 17.8	-local economy -social and solidary economy -economic activities -job creation	* in versions 2018-2016 they are described as projects developed by/for residents that promote the local economy and aim to leverage economic activities;
	- the support to employment and self-employment through the acquisition of new skills and work tools , aiming at personal and financial autonomy .	2022, 2021, 2020		4.7; 4.4 2.3 12.8	- support of employment and self-employment - new skills and work tools - personal and financial autonomy	
	the use of new technologies as a way to overcome exclusion and promote access to new sources of information	2019		10 5.b 4.4; 4.a 8.2 9.1; 9.5; 9.c 17.8	- new technologies -access to new sources of information	
	the promotion of the circular economy	2019		2.4 9.1 12.2; 12.5	- circular economy	
	the strengthening of the creative industries based in these territories	2019		4.3; 4.7; 4.a 8.9 11.4	-creative industries	
	the creation of short economic circuits that favor cooperation among local agents	2019		2.4; 2.3 4.7 8.5 9.1; 9.5 11.3	-short economic circuits	
	the internationalization of employment -generating activities in the neighborhoods	2019		2.5 4.a 8.3 11.a	-internationalization of employment	
	the exchange of knowledge with the objective of creating new skills , aiming at autonomy .	2019, 2018, 2017, 2016		4.7; 4.4 9.1 11.3	- exchange of knowledge - new skills - autonomy	
Community Space (20-2022) OR Rehabilitation and Requalification of Spaces	the (Re)qualification of public space, leisure and enjoyment spaces, on the initiative of and for the benefit of the Community , for a better spatial appropriation and creation of new functionalities , in response to new needs post Covid19 ;	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019*, 2018*, 2017*, 2016*		11.7; 11.1; 11.3; 11.4 3.4 16.7 9.1	-(re)qualification of public space -spatial appropriation - new functionalities	* before COVID (2016-2019) the theme was described as: the (re)qualification of the public space, spaces for leisure and fruition, on the initiative and for the benefit of the Community;
	- the promotion of the use of public space as a tool to combat isolation and personal and community initiatives for physical and mental health ;	2022, 2021, 2020		3.4 4.7	- public space to combat isolation - initiatives for physical and mental health;	
	- the requalification of non-residential spaces , for the installation of community services in response to new collective and personal needs;	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019*, 2018*, 2017*, 2016*		3 11.1; 11.3 9.1 16.7 4.a	- requalification of non-residential spaces -community services	* in versions 2019-2016 they are described as the requalification of non-residential spaces for the benefit of the resident population and/or destined to improve and/or increase the quality of the services provided to the Community;
	- the promotion of a Proximity Urbanism and of the Smooth Mobility ;	2022, 2020 2021**		11.2; 11.3 9.1; 9.5	- Proximity Urbanism - Smooth Mobility;	** In 2021 version the two objectives are mixed and described as:

	- the promotion of the regularization of urban planning and heritage issues (such as the cases of the ex SAAL, ex Cooperatives and AUGI's)	2022, 2020, 2019*, 2018*, 2017*, 2016*, 2021**		4.a; 4.7 11.4	- regularization of urban planning and heritage issues	-Promotion of a proximity urbanism , as well as the regularization of urban and patrimonial issues (such as the cases of the ex SAAL, ex Cooperatives and AUGI's) - Promotion of soft mobility initiatives in order to foster active and sustainable mobility *In 2016-2019 versions, this objective includes also the promotion of interventions in the built fabric
Prevention and Inclusion	- the prevention of risk behavior and violence , creating safer communities and contributing to the integration of excluded groups in society;	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019, 2018*, 2017*, 2016*		16.1 3.c; 3.7 5.2; 5.3 4.7 10.7; 10.2 11.7; 11.1 8.8	- prevention of risk behavior and violence -safe communities - integration of excluded	* In versions 2018-2016 this objective is described in two objectives: - Projects that promote prevention of risky behaviors and contribute to personal and group safety, contributing to the integration in the Community and in Society - Projects that contribute to the improvement of health care, mobility, and accessibility, promoting the social integration of the most disadvantaged
	- family and parental intervention in the most unstructured nuclei;	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019		16.2 8.7 4.2 2.2	- family and parental intervention	
	- the improvement of community services and/or the creation of new responses to old or emerging problems, facilitating local communities' access to them	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019		16.1 10.3 1.2	- adaptable and accessible community services	
	- the promotion of equal opportunities and the fight against all forms of discrimination , favoring mobility, accessibility, and social integration of the most disadvantaged	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019		10 3.6; 3.8 5.1 1.2; 1.4; 1.5 2.1 4.7 9.1 11.2; 11.3; 11.5; 11.7 16.1; 16.2; 16.10	- equal opportunities -discrimination -mobility, accessibility, and social integration	
	- promoting the use of New Technologies as a way to overcome exclusion and promote access to new sources of information ;	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019, 2018, 2017, 2016		17.8 16.10 9.c 4.a	- New Technologies for inclusivity - access to new sources of information	
	- promoting preventive actions and the mitigation of situations that affect health and well-being ;	2022, 2021*, 2020*		3; 3.c; 3.4; 3.7 11.3 4.7 2.1	- health and well-being - preventive actions	* In versions 2021-2020 this objective includes also: ...arising from the context of the state of emergency and the crisis caused by the COVID19 pandemic
	- promoting gender equality and the prevention of domestic violence .	2022, 2021		5 10.2 16.1	- gender equality - domestic violence	
Promoting Community Dynamization and Citizenship (-2022) OR	- the participation of the population in identifying and solving their problems (e.g. neighborhood problems)	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019, 2018, 2017, 2016		16.7; 16.10 11.3	- community participation -co-identification and solving neighbourhood problems	

Promotion of Citizenship	- the promotion of personal and collective initiatives to improve intergenerational and intercultural coexistence	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019, 2018, 2017, 2016		4.7 10.2	- intergenerational and intercultural coexistence	
	- the involvement of communities in promoting the quality of life of the Zones and Neighborhoods covered;	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019, 2018*, 2017*, 2016*		11.3 16.7; 16.10	- quality of life	* In versions 2018-2016 it is described as: Projects that promote co-responsibility in the quality of life in the neighborhood.
	- the education and awareness of environmental issues that contribute to green mobility, waste reduction, reuse, recovery, recycling, composting and other initiatives towards sustainable development	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019		12.5; 12.8; 12.2 13.3 11.3; 11.4; 11.6 4.7 9.1 7.a 3.d 6.b	- education and awareness of environmental issues - green mobility - waste reduction, reuse, recovery, recycling, composting - sustainable development	
	- the strengthening of forms of community self-organization ;	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019		16.7; 16.10 11.3 9.1	- community self-organization	
	- the promotion of entrepreneurial citizenship with a local focus , for the aggregation of resources and critical mass for the return to the community	2022, 2021, 2020, 2019*		8.3; 8.9 2.3; 2.5 12.6; 12.2 15.6 11.3 9.1	- entrepreneurial citizenship with a local focus - return resources to the community	* In version 2019 it is described as: the promotion of entrepreneurial citizenship
	- the promotion of parenting support and family assistance (ascendants and descendants);	2022, 2021		10.3 1.4 2.2 3.8 4.2 11.1 16.2; 16.9	- parenting support - family assistance	
	- the creation of social support and promotion of community solidarity initiatives.	2022, 2021		16.7 11.3	- social support - community solidarity	

Results

The pairs of diagrams fig. 11- fig. 12; fig. 13 - fig. 14; fig. 15 - fig. 16; fig. 17 - fig. 18; fig. 19- fig. 20, show the relevance of each SDG in each of the five themes of BIP/ZIP, while the pair fig. 21 - fig. 22 represent the combined relevance of SDGs in BIP/ZIP's objectives.

fig. 11 Spider diagram of SDGs in BIP/ZIP Theme: Improve Neighbourhood Life. Source: author.

fig. 12 Bar diagram of SDGs in BIP/ZIP Theme: Improve Neighbourhood Life. Source: author.

fig. 13 Spider diagram of SDGs in BIP/ZIP Theme: Competencies for active citizenship. Source: author

fig. 14 Bar diagram of SDGs in BIP/ZIP Theme: Competencies for active citizenship. Source: author.

fig. 15 Spider diagram of SDGs in BIP/ZIP Theme: Community Space. Source: author

fig. 16 Bar diagram of SDGs in BIP/ZIP Theme: Community Space. Source: author

fig. 17 Spider diagram of SDGs in BIP/ZIP Theme: Prevention and Inclusion. Source: author

fig. 18 Bar diagram of SDGs in BIP/ZIP Theme: Prevention and Inclusion. Source: author

fig. 19 Spider diagram of SDGs in BIP/ZIP Theme: Promoting Community Dynamization and Citizenship.
Source: author

fig. 20 Bar diagram of SDGs in BIP/ZIP Theme: Promoting Community Dynamization and Citizenship.
Source: author

fig. 21 Spider diagram of SDGs in BIP/ZIP. Source: author

fig. 22 Bar diagram of SDGs in BIP/ZIP. Source: author.

Finally, like in previous analysis, the chart in fig. 23 represents a conceptualisation of the BIP/ZIP Program as a proportion of SDGs.

BIP/ZIP Objectives and SDGs

fig. 23 SDGs in BIP/ZIP's Objectives

1.4 Comparative Results

Comparison of researcher's assessment on the relevance between SDGs and participatory budgets and the indicators by the ODS

The relative analysis in fig. 24 of Lisbon's indicators from ODS Local in fig. 3 and the BIP/ZIP's relevance per SDG in fig. 8 can have a twofold contribution. First, identify areas for improvement for BIP/ZIP, by looking into targets that are less developed, and second, showcase targets that potentially have a great relevance for Lisbon and could require further data collection from ODS Local.

fig. 24 Source: author's Analysis

Composition: Index of Themes

The three levels of analysis: global – sdgs; urban – localisation literature; and local -ODS compose an index of relevant themes per SDG and target that are handful for the context of BIP/ZIP. This is presented in Annex 3 - Themes per SDG.

Comparison: Global – Local – Specific

Looking at the juxtaposition in fig. 25 of the three produced charts that show the relevance of SDGS for participatory budgets; Lisbon; and BIP/ZIP can offer insightful conclusions.

First, the left and right charts show similar percentages, which means that the BIP/ZIP Program through its defined objectives is a very good representation of the theoretical conceptualisation of the relevance of SDGs and participatory budgets in general.

Furthermore, comparing the right and central charts, it is evident that there is still a lot of work to be done in integrating the contribution of BIP/ZIP and participatory practices in the national and local reports for sustainability.

fig. 25 Juxtaposition of: Relevance of SDGs and participatory budgets; Localised indicators per SDG for Lisbon; SDGs and specific objectives of BIP/ZIP.

2. Data driven Evaluation of BIP/ZIP

The adoption of a functional data system for the BIP/ZIP Program that integrates the SDG can not only serve the purpose of measuring its contribution to the urban sustainability of Lisbon, but as well contribute to the creation of a city-level data ecosystems that helps to break silos between various stakeholders in order to respond to local challenges.

The literature review on evaluation and classification of participatory models has identified a gap on data-driven evaluation approaches based on urban rather than policy evaluation tools and techniques, which constitutes this study an innovation in the field.

To cover this gap, this study investigates the urban analytics domain in which data-driven performance assessment is well established.

For this section, among evaluation and classification literature, a significant contribution is the work of Roberto Falanga (2019).

Methodology

Elaborated research

The data-driven evaluation section has been developed in a conference paper for the Sigradi22 conference in collaboration with Alexandra Paio, Serjoscha Duering and Angelos Chronis. This report touches upon the key methodological steps, yet a much more elaborated presentation can be found in the paper. As it is still under a publication process, it can be shared in confidentiality upon request.

Methodological steps

The development of a methodology for the data-driven evaluation of BIP/ZIP follows a process of:

- Raw data collection (Sources: BIP/ZIP documents, BIP/ZIP website, ForumUrbano) fig. 26
- Manual data collection (Mapping of Activities per project and qualitative coding of projects' activities according to an index of socio-spatial foci for sustainability) fig. 27
- Data cleaning and dataset preparation fig. 28
- Clustering of attributes to reduce the complexity of the dataset
- Dashboard development and correlations fig. 29

fig. 26 Data collection

fig. 27 Categories for qualitative coding of the BIP/ZIP activities

fig. 28 Dataset preparation

fig. 29 Interactive Dashboard and correlations

3. Self – assessment

The methodology of this study is based on input from the self-assessment of the individual projects of BIP/ZIP by the promoters and partners. This decision relates to the importance of a collaborative rather than top-down evaluation, which not only benefits the results with the expertise embedded in the people that implement the projects, but also educates the involved partners on the importance of SDGs for their future applications.

Recommendations

To implement the evaluation, the research on SDGs and the identification of themes presented in this report, can be the starting point, providing valuable knowledge. Based on the researcher's experience on the Program, useful data for collection would be:

- SDGs and specific targets to which the project responds;
- Specific issue in the targeted location that this SDG/target reflects;
- Specific activities that justify the response;
 - Status of the described activities: planned, implemented;
 - Life of the described activities: once, repeated, continuous after the completion of the project.

Some methodological suggestions for this assessment are:

- Creation of a self-assessment form - *and provide an automated method to store the responses directly in the dashboard, feeding a new "SDGs" attribute.*
- Conduct a series of workshops with the partners with the objective to:
 - explain the SDGs for the self-assessment and future applications;
 - test the assessment form and method on selected projects;
 - collect the responses and respond to questions.

References

- An integrated toolbox for deprived neighbourhoods* | URBACT (2021). Available at: <https://urbact.eu/integrated-toolbox-deprived-neighbourhoods> (Accessed: 15 January 2022).
- Annex of the 2030 Agenda (2017) 'Annex: Global Indicator Framework for the Sustainable Development Goals and Targets of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development', *Work of the Statistical Commission pertaining to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*, pp. 1–21. Available at: [https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/Global Indicator Framework_A.RES.71.313 Annex.pdf](https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/Global%20Indicator%20Framework_A.RES.71.313%20Annex.pdf).
- CML (2010) 'CARTA DOS BIP / ZIP Bairros e Zonas de Intervenção'.
- CML (2020) 'Ciclo e regras do programa BIP/ZIP Lisboa 2020 - parcerias locais', pp. 1–16. Available at: <http://habitacao.cm-lisboa.pt/documentos/1296662615D3bGB5er5Wi19HJ6.pdf>.
- CML (2022) *PROGRAMA BIP/ZIP LISBOA 2022-PARCELIAS LOCAIS CRITÉRIOS DE AVALIAÇÃO E PONTUAÇÃO DAS CANDIDATURAS PROGRAMA BIP/ZIP LISBOA 2022 PARCELIAS LOCAIS CRITÉRIOS DE AVALIAÇÃO E PONTUAÇÃO DAS CANDIDATURAS*. Available at: <https://bipzip.cm-lisboa.pt/> (Accessed: 14 September 2022).
- CML and DMHDL (2017) 'Good Practice Summary – Lisbon Local Development Strategy for Neighborhoods or Areas of Priority Intervention (BIP/ZIP): an integrated toolbox', p. 11. Available at: https://urbact.eu/sites/default/files/397_Lisbon_GPsummary.pdf.
- Falanga, R. (2019) 'Measuring citizen participation in urban regeneration: a reflection on the construction of the participation index for the Bip/Zip programme in Lisbon', *Urban Development Issues*, 62(1), pp. 47–60. doi: 10.2478/udi-2019-0009.
- Van Herck, B., Vanoeteren, V. and Janssen, K. (2019) 'Local Indicators for the 2030 Agenda (Sustainable Development Goals)'. Available at: <http://localizingthesdgs.org/library/view/620>.
- ODSlocal* (no date). Available at: <https://odslocal.pt/> (Accessed: 16 May 2022).
- Roseta, H. (2013) 'Mudar a política de habitação em Lisboa'.
- Roseta, H. (2015) 'Dos pecados urbanos à energia bip-zip', *Escutar a cidade*. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DVfzC3X6CRc>.
- United Nations General Assembly (2020) 'Global indicator framework for the Sustainable Development Goals and targets of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development', *Work of the Statistical Commission pertaining to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*, pp. 1–21. Available at: [https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/Global Indicator Framework after 2019 refinement_Eng.pdf](https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/Global%20Indicator%20Framework%20after%202019%20refinement_Eng.pdf) [https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/Global Indicator Framework_A.RES.71.313 Annex.pdf](https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/Global%20Indicator%20Framework_A.RES.71.313%20Annex.pdf).

Annex 1 – Relevance of SDS for BIP/ZIP and identification of themes – Researcher’s assessment

Legend

character	colour	details
not relevant		possible reasons: -aiming directly to developing countries - matter of national or policy level - irrelevant for the local socio-spatial context of Lisbon
relevant		presents great relevance with BIP/ZIP vision and can be further adapted to the context of BIP/ZIP
very relevant		directly connects to BIP/ZIP
relevant at the policy level		relates to BIP/ZIP as an overall policy, but is unlikely to be translated to a project-based context

Table

Sustainable Development Goals and Targets	relevance to BIP/ZIP	themes
1.1 By 2030, eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day		-poverty
1.2 By 2030, reduce at least by half the proportion of men, women and children of all ages living in poverty in all its dimensions according to national definitions		- poverty
1.3 Implement nationally appropriate social protection systems and measures for all, including floors, and by 2030 achieve substantial coverage of the poor and the vulnerable		- substantial coverage of the poor and vulnerable
1.4 By 2030, ensure that all men and women, in particular the poor and the vulnerable, have equal rights to economic resources, as well as access to basic services, ownership and control over land and other forms of property, inheritance, natural resources, appropriate new technology and financial services, including microfinance		- equal rights to economic resources - access to basic services -access to ownership and control over land - access to property - access to inheritance - access to natural resources - access to appropriate new technology - access to financial services, including microfinance

1.5 By 2030, build the resilience of the poor and those in vulnerable situations and reduce their exposure and vulnerability to climate-related extreme events and other economic, social and environmental shocks and disasters		- resilience for poor and vulnerable
1.a Ensure significant mobilization of resources from a variety of sources, including through enhanced development cooperation, in order to provide adequate and predictable means for developing countries, in particular least developed countries, to implement programmes and policies to end poverty in all its dimensions		//developing countries
1.b Create sound policy frameworks at the national, regional and international levels, based on pro-poor and gender-sensitive development strategies, to support accelerated investment in poverty eradication actions		- pro-poor and gender-sensitive development strategies - investment in poverty eradication actions
2.1 By 2030, end hunger and ensure access by all people, in particular the poor and people in vulnerable situations, including infants, to safe, nutritious and sufficient food all year round		- access to safe, nutritious and sufficient food all year round
2.2 By 2030, end all forms of malnutrition, including achieving, by 2025, the internationally agreed targets on stunting and wasting in children under 5 years of age, and address the nutritional needs of adolescent girls, pregnant and lactating women and older persons		- end all forms of malnutrition - stunting and wasting in children under 5 years of age - nutritional needs of adolescent girls, pregnant and lactating women and older persons
2.3 By 2030, double the agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers, in particular women, indigenous peoples, family farmers, pastoralists and fishers, including through secure and equal access to land, other productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment		- small/local farming - secure and equal access to land - access to productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment
2.4 By 2030, ensure sustainable food production systems and implement resilient agricultural practices that increase productivity and production, that help maintain ecosystems, that strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change, extreme weather, drought, flooding and other disasters and that progressively improve land and soil quality		- sustainable food production - resilient agricultural practices - strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change
2.5 By 2020, maintain the genetic diversity of seeds, cultivated plants and farmed and domesticated animals and their related wild species, including through soundly managed and diversified seed and plant banks at the national, regional and international levels, and promote access to and fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources and associated traditional knowledge, as internationally agreed		- diversity of seeds, plants and farmed and domesticated animals and their related wild species - seed and plant banks - fair and equitable sharing of commons
2.a Increase investment, including through enhanced international cooperation, in rural infrastructure, agricultural research and extension services, technology development and plant and livestock gene banks in order to enhance agricultural productive capacity in developing countries, in particular least developed countries		- agricultural research and extension services -technology development and plant and livestock gene banks //developing countries
2.b Correct and prevent trade restrictions and distortions in world agricultural markets, including through the parallel elimination of all forms of agricultural export subsidies and all export measures with equivalent effect, in accordance with the mandate of the Doha Development Round		// national level
2.c Adopt measures to ensure the proper functioning of food commodity markets and their derivatives and facilitate timely access to market information, including on food reserves, in order to help limit extreme food price volatility		- food commodity markets // policy level
3.1 By 2030, reduce the global maternal mortality ratio to less than 70 per 100,000 live births		- mortality rate // global level
3.2 By 2030, end preventable deaths of newborns and children under 5 years of age, with all countries aiming to reduce neonatal mortality to at least as low as 12 per 1,000 live births and under-5 mortality to at least as low as 25 per 1,000 live births		// national level
3.3 By 2030, end the epidemics of AIDS, tuberculosis, malaria and neglected tropical diseases and combat hepatitis, water-borne diseases and other communicable diseases		// global level

3.4 By 2030, reduce by one third premature mortality from non-communicable diseases through prevention and treatment and promote mental health and well-being		- prevention and treatment of non-communicable diseases - mental health and well-being promotion
3.5 Strengthen the prevention and treatment of substance abuse, including narcotic drug abuse and harmful use of alcohol		- substance abuse
3.6 By 2020, halve the number of global deaths and injuries from road traffic accidents		- traffic accidents
3.7 By 2030, ensure universal access to sexual and reproductive health-care services, including for family planning, information and education, and the integration of reproductive health into national strategies and programmes		- access to sexual and reproductive health care services - reproductive health education and information
3.8 Achieve universal health coverage, including financial risk protection, access to quality essential health-care services and access to safe, effective, quality and affordable essential medicines and vaccines for all		- access to health-care services - access to safe, effective, quality and affordable essential medicines and vaccines
3.9 By 2030, substantially reduce the number of deaths and illnesses from hazardous chemicals and air, water and soil pollution and contamination		- pollution and contamination
3.a Strengthen the implementation of the World Health Organization Framework Convention on Tobacco Control in all countries, as appropriate		- tobacco control //national level
3.b Support the research and development of vaccines and medicines for the communicable and non-communicable diseases that primarily affect developing countries, provide access to affordable essential medicines and vaccines, in accordance with the Doha Declaration on the TRIPS Agreement and Public Health, which affirms the right of developing countries to use to the full the provisions in the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights regarding flexibilities to protect public health, and, in particular, provide access to medicines for all		//national level
3.c Substantially increase health financing and the recruitment, development, training and retention of the health workforce in developing countries, especially in least developed countries and small island developing States		//developing countries
3.d Strengthen the capacity of all countries, in particular developing countries, for early warning, risk reduction and management of national and global health risks		- risk reduction on national and global health risks
4.1 By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes		- quality primary and secondary education
4.2 By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care and pre-primary education so that they are ready for primary education		- pre-school education and childcare
4.3 By 2030, ensure equal access for all women and men to affordable and quality technical, vocational and tertiary education, including university		- adult education - professional training
4.4 By 2030, substantially increase the number of youth and adults who have relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship		- development of professional skills for employability
4.5 By 2030, eliminate gender disparities in education and ensure equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for the vulnerable, including persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples and children in vulnerable situations		- disparities in education (gender, vulnerability, disabilities)
4.6 By 2030, ensure that all youth and a substantial proportion of adults, both men and women, achieve literacy and numeracy		- literacy and numeracy

<p>4.7 By 2030, ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including, among others, through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship and appreciation of cultural diversity and of culture's contribution to sustainable development</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - education for sustainable development - education for sustainable lifestyles - education for human rights - education for gender equality - promotion peace and non-violence - promotion of global citizenship - appreciation of cultural diversity - appreciation of culture's contribution to sustainable development
<p>4.a Build and upgrade education facilities that are child, disability and gender sensitive and provide safe, non-violent, inclusive and effective learning environments for all</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - inclusive educational facilities
<p>4.b By 2020, substantially expand globally the number of scholarships available to developing countries, in particular least developed countries, small island developing States and African countries, for enrolment in higher education, including vocational training and information and communications technology, technical, engineering and scientific programmes, in developed countries and other developing countries</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scholarships // developing countries

4.c By 2030, substantially increase the supply of qualified teachers, including through international cooperation for teacher training in developing countries, especially least developed countries and small island developing States		- qualified teachers //focus on developing countries
5.1 End all forms of discrimination against all women and girls everywhere		- female discrimination
5.2 Eliminate all forms of violence against all women and girls in the public and private spheres, including trafficking and sexual and other types of exploitation		- violence against women
5.3 Eliminate all harmful practices, such as child, early and forced marriage and female genital mutilation		- harmful practices against women
5.4 Recognize and value unpaid care and domestic work through the provision of public services, infrastructure and social protection policies and the promotion of shared responsibility within the household and the family as nationally appropriate		//policy level
5.5 Ensure women's full and effective participation and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and public life		- female political participation
5.6 Ensure universal access to sexual and reproductive health and reproductive rights as agreed in accordance with the Programme of Action of the International Conference on Population and Development and the Beijing Platform for Action and the outcome documents of their review conferences		- access to sexual and reproductive health and re- productive rights
5.a Undertake reforms to give women equal rights to economic resources, as well as access to ownership and control over land and other forms of property, financial services, inheritance and natural resources, in accordance with national laws		//policy level
5.b Enhance the use of enabling technology, in particular information and communications technology, to promote the empowerment of women		- women empowerment through technology
5.c Adopt and strengthen sound policies and enforceable legislation for the promotion of gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls at all levels		//policy level
6.1 By 2030, achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all		- safe and affordable drinking water
6.2 By 2030, achieve access to adequate and equitable sanitation and hygiene for all and end open defecation, paying special attention to the needs of women and girls and those in vulnerable situations		- access to sanitation and hygiene
6.3 By 2030, improve water quality by reducing pollution, eliminating dumping and minimizing release of hazardous chemicals and materials, halving the proportion of untreated wastewater and substantially increasing recycling and safe reuse globally		//not relevant context
6.4 By 2030, substantially increase water-use efficiency across all sectors and ensure sustainable withdrawals and supply of freshwater to address water scarcity and substantially reduce the number of people suffering from water scarcity		// not relevant context
6.5 By 2030, implement integrated water resources management at all levels, including through transboundary cooperation as appropriate		- water resources management //national (?)
6.6 By 2020, protect and restore water-related ecosystems, including mountains, forests, wetlands, rivers, aquifers and lakes		- ecosystem protection // not relevant context
6.a By 2030, expand international cooperation and capacity-building support to developing countries in water- and sanitation-related activities and programmes, including water harvesting, desalination, water efficiency, wastewater treatment, recycling and reuse technologies		//developing countries
6.b Support and strengthen the participation of local communities in improving water and sanitation management		- participatory water management - sanitation
7.1 By 2030, ensure universal access to affordable, reliable and modern energy services		- affordable energy

7.2 By 2030, increase substantially the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix		//global focus
7.3 By 2030, double the global rate of improvement in energy efficiency		- energy efficiency //policy level
7.a By 2030, enhance international cooperation to facilitate access to clean energy research and technology, including renewable energy, energy efficiency and advanced and cleaner fossil-fuel technology, and promote investment in energy infrastructure and clean energy technology		- access to clean energy research and technology
7.b By 2030, expand infrastructure and upgrade technology for supplying modern and sustainable energy services for all in developing countries, in particular least developed countries, small island developing States and landlocked developing countries, in accordance with their respective programmes of support		- energy infrastructure //wider scale
8.1 Sustain per capita economic growth in accordance with national circumstances and, in particular, at least 7 per cent gross domestic product growth per annum in the least developed countries		- economic growth //developing countries
8.2 Achieve higher levels of economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading and innovation, including through a focus on high-value added and labour-intensive sectors		- economic productivity - technological innovation
8.3 Promote development-oriented policies that support productive activities, decent job creation, entrepreneurship, creativity and innovation, and encourage the formalization and growth of micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises, including through access to financial services		- productive activities - job creation - entrepreneurship - creativity and innovation - micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises
8.4 Improve progressively, through 2030, global resource efficiency in consumption and production and endeavour to decouple economic growth from environmental degradation, in accordance with the 10-Year Framework of Programmes on Sustainable Consumption and Production, with developed countries taking the lead		//global focus
8.5 By 2030, achieve full and productive employment and decent work for all women and men, including for young people and persons with disabilities, and equal pay for work of equal value		- inclusive employment - decent work
8.6 By 2020, substantially reduce the proportion of youth not in employment, education or training		- youth unemployment
8.7 Take immediate and effective measures to eradicate forced labour, end modern slavery and human trafficking and secure the prohibition and elimination of the worst forms of child labour, including recruitment and use of child soldiers, and by 2025 end child labour in all its forms		- eradicate forced labour/ slavery and human trafficking/ child labour - child soldiers
8.8 Protect labour rights and promote safe and secure working environments for all workers, including migrant workers, in particular women migrants, and those in precarious employment		- safe and secure working environments - secure working for migrant workers
8.9 By 2030, devise and implement policies to promote sustainable tourism that creates jobs and promotes local culture and products		- sustainable tourism - tourism and job creation - promotion of local culture and products
8.10 Strengthen the capacity of domestic financial institutions to encourage and expand access to banking, insurance and financial services for all		- access to banking and financial services
8.a Increase Aid for Trade support for developing countries, in particular least developed countries, including through the Enhanced Integrated Framework for Trade-related Technical Assistance to Least Developed Countries		// developing countries
8.b By 2020, develop and operationalize a global strategy for youth employment and implement the Global Jobs Pact of the International Labour Organization		//global strategy
9.1 Develop quality, reliable, sustainable and resilient infrastructure, including regional and transborder infrastructure, to support economic development and human well-being, with a focus on affordable and equitable access for all		- sustainable and resilient infrastructure for economic development and human well-being - affordable and equitable access to resilient infrastructure

9.2 Promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and, by 2030, significantly raise industry's share of employment and gross domestic product, in line with national circumstances, and double its share in least developed countries		
9.3 Increase the access of small-scale industrial and other enterprises, in particular in developing countries, to financial services, including affordable credit, and their integration into value chains and markets		- financial services for small-scale enterprises // national level, in particular developing countries
9.4 By 2030, upgrade infrastructure and retrofit industries to make them sustainable, with increased resource-use efficiency and greater adoption of clean and environmentally sound technologies and industrial processes, with all countries taking action in accordance with their respective capabilities		- retrofit industries to resource-use efficiency and clean technologies //industry level
9.5 Enhance scientific research, upgrade the technological capabilities of industrial sectors in all countries, in particular developing countries, including, by 2030, encouraging innovation and substantially increasing the number of research and development workers per 1 million people and public and private research and development spending		- scientific research and technological capabilities of industrial sectors // national level, in particular developing countries
9.a Facilitate sustainable and resilient infrastructure development in developing countries through enhanced financial, technological and technical support to African countries, least developed countries, landlocked developing countries and small island developing States		// developing countries
9.b Support domestic technology development, research and innovation in developing countries, including by ensuring a conducive policy environment for, inter alia, industrial diversification and value addition to commodities		// developing countries
9.c Significantly increase access to information and communications technology and strive to provide universal and affordable access to the Internet in least developed countries by 2020		- access to information and communications technology - internet access
10.1 By 2030, progressively achieve and sustain income growth of the bottom 40 per cent of the population at a rate higher than the national average		- income growth //policy level
10.2 By 2030, empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status		- social, economic and political inclusion of all (age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status)
10.3 Ensure equal opportunity and reduce inequalities of outcome, including by eliminating discriminatory laws, policies and practices and promoting appropriate legislation, policies and action in this regard		- equal opportunity and outcome
10.4 Adopt policies, especially fiscal, wage and social protection policies, and progressively achieve greater equality		//policy level
10.5 Improve the regulation and monitoring of global financial markets and institutions and strengthen the implementation of such regulations		//policy level
10.6 Ensure enhanced representation and voice for developing countries in decision-making in global international economic and financial institutions in order to deliver more effective, credible, accountable and legitimate institutions		// developing countries
10.7 Facilitate orderly, safe, regular and responsible migration and mobility of people, including through the implementation of planned and well-managed migration policies		- safe, regular and responsible migration and mobility of people
10.a Implement the principle of special and differential treatment for developing countries, in particular least developed countries, in accordance with World Trade Organization agreements		// developing countries
10.b Encourage official development assistance and financial flows, including foreign direct investment, to States where the need is greatest, in particular least developed countries, African countries, small island developing States and landlocked developing countries, in accordance with their national plans and programmes		// developing countries
10.c By 2030, reduce to less than 3 per cent the transaction costs of migrant remittances and eliminate remittance corridors with costs higher than 5 per cent		//international level

11.1 By 2030, ensure access for all to adequate, safe and affordable housing and basic services and upgrade slums		- safe and affordable housing - slums upgrade - access to basic services
11.2 By 2030, provide access to safe, affordable, accessible and sustainable transport systems for all, improving road safety, notably by expanding public transport, with special attention to the needs of those in vulnerable situations, women, children, persons with disabilities and older persons		- sustainable transport systems - road safety - public transport - inclusive transport
11.3 By 2030, enhance inclusive and sustainable urbanization and capacity for participatory, integrated and sustainable human settlement planning and management in all countries		- inclusive and sustainable urbanization - participatory urbanism - integrated planning and management
11.4 Strengthen efforts to protect and safeguard the world's cultural and natural heritage		- cultural and natural heritage protection
11.5 By 2030, significantly reduce the number of deaths and the number of people affected and substantially decrease the direct economic losses relative to global gross domestic product caused by disasters, including water-related disasters, with a focus on protecting the poor and people in vulnerable situations		- protect the poor by economic disasters
11.6 By 2030, reduce the adverse per capita environmental impact of cities, including by paying special attention to air quality and municipal and other waste management		- waste management
11.7 By 2030, provide universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible, green and public spaces, in particular for women and children, older persons and persons with disabilities		- safe, inclusive and accessible, green and public spaces
11.a Support positive economic, social and environmental links between urban, peri-urban and rural areas by strengthening national and regional development planning		- economic, social and environmental links
11.b By 2020, substantially increase the number of cities and human settlements adopting and implementing integrated policies and plans towards inclusion, resource efficiency, mitigation and adaptation to climate change, resilience to disasters, and develop and implement, in line with the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030, holistic disaster risk management at all levels		//integrated policies
11.c Support least developed countries, including through financial and technical assistance, in building sustainable and resilient buildings utilizing local materials		//least developed countries
12.1 Implement the 10-Year Framework of Programmes on Sustainable Consumption and Production Patterns, all countries taking action, with developed countries taking the lead, taking into account the development and capabilities of developing countries		//national level
12.2 By 2030, achieve the sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources		- sustainable management of natural resources
12.3 By 2030, halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses		- food loss
12.4 By 2020, achieve the environmentally sound management of chemicals and all wastes throughout their life cycle, in accordance with agreed international frameworks, and significantly reduce their release to air, water and soil in order to minimize their adverse impacts on human health and the environment		- waste management
12.5 By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse		- recycling and reuse
12.6 Encourage companies, especially large and transnational companies, to adopt sustainable practices and to integrate sustainability information into their reporting cycle		- sustainable companies
12.7 Promote public procurement practices that are sustainable, in accordance with national policies and priorities		// national level
12.8 By 2030, ensure that people everywhere have the relevant information and awareness for sustainable development and lifestyles in harmony with nature		- access to information on resilience
12.a Support developing countries to strengthen their scientific and technological capacity to move towards more sustainable patterns of consumption and production		//developing countries

12.b Develop and implement tools to monitor sustainable development impacts for sustainable tourism that creates jobs and promotes local culture and products		- monitor sustainable tourism
12.c Rationalize inefficient fossil-fuel subsidies that encourage wasteful consumption by removing market distortions, in accordance with national circumstances, including by restructuring taxation and phasing out those harmful subsidies, where they exist, to reflect their environmental impacts, taking fully into account the specific needs and conditions of developing countries and minimizing the possible adverse impacts on their development in a manner that protects the poor and the affected communities		//policy level
13.1 Strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters in all countries		// national level
13.2 Integrate climate change measures into national policies, strategies and planning		// national level
13.3 Improve education, awareness-raising and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction and early warning		- climate change mitigation and adaptation education - awareness-raising on climate change - human and institutional capacity on climate change
13.a Implement the commitment undertaken by developed-country parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change to a goal of mobilizing jointly \$100 billion annually by 2020 from all sources to address the needs of developing countries in the context of meaningful mitigation actions and transparency on implementation and fully operationalize the Green Climate Fund through its capitalization as soon as possible		// national level
13.b Promote mechanisms for raising capacity for effective climate change-related planning and management in least developed countries and small island developing States, including focusing on women, youth and local and marginalized communities		// national level
14.1 By 2025, prevent and significantly reduce marine pollution of all kinds, in particular from land-based activities, including marine debris and nutrient pollution		//not relevant context
14.2 By 2020, sustainably manage and protect marine and coastal ecosystems to avoid significant adverse impacts, including by strengthening their resilience, and take action for their restoration in order to achieve healthy and productive oceans		//not relevant context
14.3 Minimize and address the impacts of ocean acidification, including through enhanced scientific cooperation at all levels		//not relevant context
14.4 By 2020, effectively regulate harvesting and end overfishing, illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing and destructive fishing practices and implement science-based management plans, in order to restore fish stocks in the shortest time feasible, at least to levels that can produce maximum sustainable yield as determined by their biological characteristics		//not relevant context
14.5 By 2020, conserve at least 10 per cent of coastal and marine areas, consistent with national and international law and based on the best available scientific information		//not relevant context
14.6 By 2020, prohibit certain forms of fisheries subsidies which contribute to overcapacity and overfishing, eliminate subsidies that contribute to illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing and refrain from introducing new such subsidies, recognizing that appropriate and effective special and differential treatment for developing and least developed countries should be an integral part of the World Trade Organization fisheries subsidies negotiation ⁴		//not relevant context
14.7 By 2030, increase the economic benefits to small island developing States and least developed countries from the sustainable use of marine resources, including through sustainable management of fisheries, aquaculture and tourism		//not relevant context
14.a Increase scientific knowledge, develop research capacity and transfer marine technology, taking into account the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission Criteria and Guidelines on the Transfer of Marine Technology, in order to improve ocean health and to enhance the contribution of marine biodiversity to the development of developing countries, in		//not relevant context

particular small island developing States and least developed countries		
14.b Provide access for small-scale artisanal fishers to marine resources and markets		//not relevant context
14.c Enhance the conservation and sustainable use of oceans and their resources by implementing international law as reflected in the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, which provides the legal framework for the conservation and sustainable use of oceans and their resources, as recalled in paragraph 158 of "The future we want"		//not relevant context
15.1 By 2020, ensure the conservation, restoration and sustainable use of terrestrial and inland freshwater ecosystems and their services, in particular forests, wetlands, mountains and drylands, in line with obligations under international agreements		- forests, wetlands, mountains and drylands
15.2 By 2020, promote the implementation of sustainable management of all types of forests, halt deforestation, restore degraded forests and substantially increase afforestation and reforestation globally		//not relevant context
15.3 By 2030, combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil, including land affected by desertification, drought and floods, and strive to achieve a land degradation-neutral world		//not relevant context
15.4 By 2030, ensure the conservation of mountain ecosystems, including their biodiversity, in order to enhance their capacity to provide benefits that are essential for sustainable development		//not relevant context
15.5 Take urgent and significant action to reduce the degradation of natural habitats, halt the loss of biodiversity and, by 2020, protect and prevent the extinction of threatened species		//not relevant context
15.6 Promote fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources and promote appropriate access to such resources, as internationally agreed		- fair and equitable genetic commons resources
15.7 Take urgent action to end poaching and trafficking of protected species of flora and fauna and address both demand and supply of illegal wildlife products		//not relevant context
15.8 By 2020, introduce measures to prevent the introduction and significantly reduce the impact of invasive alien species on land and water ecosystems and control or eradicate the priority species		//not relevant context
15.9 By 2020, integrate ecosystem and biodiversity values into national and local planning, development processes, poverty reduction strategies and accounts		//policy level
15.a Mobilize and significantly increase financial resources from all sources to conserve and sustainably use biodiversity and ecosystems		- biodiversity and ecosystems conservation and sustainable use
15.b Mobilize significant resources from all sources and at all levels to finance sustainable forest management and provide adequate incentives to developing countries to advance such management, including for conservation and reforestation		//not relevant context
15.c Enhance global support for efforts to combat poaching and trafficking of protected species, including by increasing the capacity of local communities to pursue sustainable livelihood opportunities		//broad focus
16.1 Significantly reduce all forms of violence and related death rates everywhere		- reduce violence
16.2 End abuse, exploitation, trafficking and all forms of violence against and torture of children		- end child abuse
16.3 Promote the rule of law at the national and international levels and ensure equal access to justice for all		-very much oriented to national level

16.4 By 2030, significantly reduce illicit financial and arms flows, strengthen the recovery and return of stolen assets and combat all forms of organized crime		- combat all forms of organized crime
16.5 Substantially reduce corruption and bribery in all their forms		- reduce corruption
16.6 Develop effective, accountable and transparent institutions at all levels		- effective, accountable and transparent institutions
16.7 Ensure responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making at all levels		- responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making
16.8 Broaden and strengthen the participation of developing countries in the institutions of global governance		//developing countries
16.9 By 2030, provide legal identity for all, including birth registration		- legal identity - birth registration
16.10 Ensure public access to information and protect fundamental freedoms, in accordance with national legislation and international agreements		- public access to information - fundamental freedoms
16.a Strengthen relevant national institutions, including through international cooperation, for building capacity at all levels, in particular in developing countries, to prevent violence and combat terrorism and crime		//very much oriented to national level
16.b Promote and enforce non-discriminatory laws and policies for sustainable development		//BIP/ZIP policy
Finance		
17.1 Strengthen domestic resource mobilization, including through international support to developing countries, to improve domestic capacity for tax and other revenue collection		//developing countries
17.2 Developed countries to implement fully their official development assistance commitments, including the commitment by many developed countries to achieve the target of 0.7 per cent of gross national income for official development assistance (ODA/GNI) to developing countries and 0.15 to 0.20 per cent of ODA/GNI to least developed countries; ODA providers are encouraged to consider setting a target to provide at least 0.20 per cent of ODA/GNI to least developed countries		//developing countries
17.3 Mobilize additional financial resources for developing countries from multiple sources		//developing countries
17.4 Assist developing countries in attaining long-term debt sustainability through coordinated policies aimed at fostering debt financing, debt relief and debt restructuring, as appropriate, and address the external debt of highly indebted poor countries to reduce debt distress		//developing countries
17.5 Adopt and implement investment promotion regimes for least developed countries		//very much oriented to national level
Technology		
17.6 Enhance North-South, South-South and triangular regional and international cooperation on and access to science, technology and innovation and enhance knowledge-sharing on mutually agreed terms, including through improved coordination among existing mechanisms, in particular at the United Nations level, and through a global technology facilitation mechanism		//global focus
17.7 Promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies to developing countries on favourable terms, including on concessional and preferential terms, as mutually agreed		//developing countries
17.8 Fully operationalize the technology bank and science, technology and innovation capacity-building mechanism for least developed countries by 2017 and enhance the use of enabling technology, in particular information and communications technology		- technology bank - science, technology and innovation capacity-building mechanism //least developed countries
Capacity-building		
17.9 Enhance international support for implementing effective and targeted capacity-building in developing countries to support national plans to implement all the Sustainable Development Goals,		//developing countries

including through North-South, South-South and triangular cooperation		
Trade		
17.10 Promote a universal, rules-based, open, non-discriminatory and equitable multilateral trading system under the World Trade Organization, including through the conclusion of negotiations under its Doha Development Agenda		//international level
17.11 Significantly increase the exports of developing countries, in particular with a view to doubling the least developed countries' share of global exports by 2020		//developing countries
17.12 Realize timely implementation of duty-free and quota-free market access on a lasting basis for all least developed countries, consistent with World Trade Organization decisions, including by ensuring that preferential rules of origin applicable to imports from least developed countries are transparent and simple, and contribute to facilitating market access		// very much oriented to national level
Systemic issues		
<i>Policy and institutional coherence</i>		
17.13 Enhance global macroeconomic stability, including through policy coordination and policy coherence		//very much oriented to national level
17.14 Enhance policy coherence for sustainable development		- policy coherence //policy level
17.15 Respect each country's policy space and leadership to establish and implement policies for poverty eradication and sustainable development		// BIP/ZIP IS such a policy
<i>Multi-stakeholder partnerships</i>		
17.16 Enhance the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development, complemented by multi-stakeholder partnerships that mobilize and share knowledge, expertise, technology and financial resources, to support the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals in all countries, in particular developing countries		relevant at the policy level
17.17 Encourage and promote effective public, public-private and civil society partnerships, building on the experience and resourcing strategies of partnerships		- public, public-private and civil society partnerships //also relevant at the policy level
<i>Data, monitoring and accountability</i>		
17.18 By 2020, enhance capacity-building support to developing countries, including for least developed countries and small island developing States, to increase significantly the availability of high-quality, timely and reliable data disaggregated by income, gender, age, race, ethnicity, migratory status, disability, geographic location and other characteristics relevant in national contexts		// developing countries
17.19 By 2030, build on existing initiatives to develop measurements of progress on sustainable development that complement gross domestic product, and support statistical capacity-building in developing countries		// developing countries

Annex 2 - SDGs that apply to the context of Lisbon and identification of themes - Based on ODSLocal

List of SDGs that apply to the context of Lisbon (Based on ODSLocal)

target	indicator	themes
1.2	Beneficiaries of social insertion income, social security per 1000 inhabitants of working age (‰)	social aid
1.3	Proportion of beneficiaries of social security sickness benefits in relation to the working-age population (15-64 years) (%)	sickness benefits for working-age population
1.3	Proportion of new beneficiaries of social security unemployment benefits in relation to the working-age population (15-64) (%)	unemployment benefits
1.4	Proportion of households served by wastewater drainage (%)	households access to wastewater drainage
1.4	Ratio of rental housing values to income %)	housing affordability
1.4	Proportion of households served by water supply (%)	access to water supply
1.A	Proportion of community participation in co-financed projects in the total capital revenues of municipalities (%)	community participation in co-financed projects
1.A	Proportion of purchases of capital goods in the total expenses of municipalities (%)	capital goods
2.3	Gross value added in agriculture, livestock and fisheries per employee	agri-prosumerism
2.4	Proportion of agricultural area used for small farming (%)	small farming
3.1	Five-year maternal mortality ratio per 100000 live births	mortality (general and specific)
3.2	Five-year rate of infant (0 to 4 years) deaths per 1000 live births (‰)	
3.2	Five-year neonatal mortality rate (‰)	
3.3	Five-year mortality rate from viral hepatitis per 100mil population	
3.3	Five-year mortality rate from human immunodeficiency virus [HIV] per 100mil population	
3.4	5-year rate of standardized premature mortality (before the age of 75) per 100mil population	
3.4	Five-year mortality rate from suicide and self-harm per 100mil population	
3.4	5-yearly standardized mortality rate from diabetes mellitus per 100mil population	
3.6	Severity rate of traffic accidents with victims (n°)	traffic accidents
3.7	5-year rate of live births to adolescent mothers (%)	birth rates
3.7	Medical specialists (gynaecology-obstetrics) per 10mil women of childbearing age (15-49 years) (no.)	access to sexual and reproductive health care services
3.8	Doctors per 1000 inhabitants (no.)	access to health system and medical facilities
3.8	Nurses per 1000 inhabitants per workplace (no.)	access to health human resources
3.8	Pharmacies and mobile pharmaceutical units per 1000 inhabitants (no.)	access to pharmacies
3.9	Deaths from respiratory system diseases per 10000 population (no.)	respiratory disease mortality rate
3.9	Deaths from accidental poisoning (intoxication) by drugs, medicines and biological substances per 10000 inhabitants (no.)	health education on medical substances
3.A	Five-yearly standardized mortality rate for malignant tumor of the larynx, trachea, bronchi and lungs, per 100000 population	tumor mortality rate
4.1	Transition / completion rate in secondary education (%)	quality primary and secondary education
4.1	Transition/completion rate in basic education (%)	basic education
4.2	Proportion of public and private pre-school establishments dependent on the State	pre-school establishments
4.2	Gross pre-schooling rate (%)	pre-school education and childcare
4.3	Participation rate in double certification courses in youth-oriented secondary education (%)	double certificate courses in youth-oriented secondary education
4.3	Proportion of individuals aged 18 and over who participated in adult education and training courses	adult education
4.4	Average number of students per computer with Internet connection enrolled in non-higher education (no.)	access to internet
4.6	Gross enrolment ratio in basic education (%)	
4.6	Gross enrolment ratio in secondary education (%)	
4.A	Average number of pupils per computer enrolled in non-tertiary education (no.)	access to computers
5.1	Disparity in average monthly earnings (Between genders - %) of the employed population	gender wage gap

5.2	Domestic violence against spouse or similar per 1000 population (no.)	domestic violence against women
5.4	Ratio of length of initial social security parental leave of father and mother (%)	parental leave
5.5	Proportion of women elected to Municipal Councils in local elections (%)	female political participation in local authorities
6	Losses in water supply systems (%)	
6	Proportion of drained wastewater routed to wastewater treatment plants (%)	wastewater treatment
6.1	Proportion of households served by water supply (%)	households access to water
6.1	Safe water (percentage of water controlled and of good quality for human consumption) (%)	safe water
6.2	Proportion of households served by wastewater drainage (%)	households access to wastewater drainage
6.3	Proportion of surface water bodies area with overall "good and above" status (%)	surface water
7.3	Electricity consumption per inhabitant (kWh/inhabitant)	access to electricity
7.A	Municipality with Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan and monitoring report (in the scope of the Covenant of Mayors)	
8	Foreign visitors to museums (n°)	foreign visitors to museums
8.1	Gross declared income less personal income tax (PIT) per capita relative to the national value (%)	declared income
8.5	Personnel employed in establishments per 100 resident individuals aged 15 or over	employment rate
8.5	Proportion of new beneficiaries of social security unemployment benefits in relation to the population of working age (15-64) (%)	unemployment benefits
8.5	Disparity in average monthly earnings (between genders - %) of the employed population	gender income disparity salary
8.5	Average monthly earnings in the municipality in relation to the national value (%)	
8.1	Establishments of other monetary intermediation (banks, savings banks and mutual agricultural credit banks) per 10,000 inhabitants (No.)	banks
8.1	ATMs per 10,000 inhabitants (no.)	ATMs
9	Municipal environmental expenditure per inhabitant (€/inhab.)	municipal environmental expenditure
9.1	Proportion of community participation in co-financed projects in the total capital revenues of municipalities (%)	community participation
9.B	Proportion of legal persons and similar entities engaged in consulting, scientific, technical and similar activities (%)	legal persons
9.C	Broadband Internet access at fixed location per 100 inhabitants (No.)	internet connection
10.1	Inequality in the distribution of gross declared income of taxable persons (P80/P20) (No.)	income inequality
10.1	Gini coefficient of gross income declared per tax household (%)	household income distribution
10.2	Median value of gross income declared per taxpayer in the municipality in relation to the median value in Portugal (%)	territorial income distribution
10.2	Median monthly income in the municipality in relation to the national value (%)	
10.4	Redistributive impact of income tax policy	
11.1	Ratio between housing rental values and income (%)	housing affordability
11.3	Evolution of the efficiency of the artificialized territories per inhabitant (%)	artificialised territories
11.4	Municipal expenditure on protecting biodiversity and landscape per inhabitant (€/inhab.)	biodiversity protection
11.4	Municipalities' expenditure on cultural heritage per inhabitant (€/inhab.)	cultural heritage protection
11.4	Visitors to museums per inhabitant (no.)	visitors to museums
11.5	Burnt forest area rate (%)	burnt forest areas
11.5	Inhabitants per firefighter (no.)	no of firefighters
11.6	Proportion of urban waste selectively collected (%)	urban waste collection
11.6	Proportion of urban waste landfilled (%)	urban landfills
11.6	Urban waste collected per inhabitant (kg/inhab.)	
12.5	Urban waste collected per inhabitant (kg/inhab.)	urban waste collection
12.5	Proportion of urban waste selectively collected (%)	
12.5	Proportion of municipal waste prepared for reuse and recycling (%)	reuse and recycling
12.5	Landfill of biodegradable municipal waste (%)	landfills
13	Proportion of surface area of forest intervention areas (%)	forest areas
13.1	Proportion of surface of classified areas (%)	
13.2	Covenant of Mayors (membership and progress)	
13.2	Greenhouse gas emissions (kt CO ₂ eq)	greenhouse emissions
13.3	Non-governmental environmental organization members per 1000 inhabitants (no.)	environmental NGOs
14.1	Plastic collected (t) per 10,000 inhabitants	plastic collection
15	Proportion of area of forest intervention areas (%)	forest areas
15.1	Proportion of surface of classified areas (%)	
15.1	Proportion of water bodies with good status / ecological potential (%)	quality water bodies
15.2	Forest fire fighters per 10 km ² of forest area (No.)	forest firefighters
15.2	Rate of burnt forest area (%)	burnt forest areas
15.3	Artificialized land per capita (m ² /inhab.)	artificialised land
15.A	Municipalities' expenditure on biodiversity and landscape protection per capita (€/hab.)	biodiversity protection

16	Crime rate (‰)	crime rate
16.1	Crimes against life in society per 10 000 inhabitants	crimes against society
16.1	Crimes against property per 10 000 inhabitants	crimes against property
16.1	Crimes against persons per 10 000 inhabitants	crimes against individuals
16.3	Crimes against the State per 10 000 inhabitants	crimes against the state
16.6	Ratio of municipal debt to revenue (%)	municipal debt
16.6	Municipal Transparency Index	municipal transparency
16.7	Abstention rate in municipal elections (%)	abstention from voting in municipal elections
16.1	Gender disparity in average monthly earnings of the employed population (%)	gender income disparity
17.1	Share of taxes in total revenues of Municipalities (%)	municipalities taxes
17.1	Ratio between Municipal Council revenues and expenditures (%)	municipal revenue and expenditures
17.1	Local government revenue per inhabitant (€/inhabitant)	
17.1	Municipal council debt per inhabitant (€/inhab.)	
17.6	Broadband Internet access at a fixed location per 100 inhabitants (No.)	internet access
17.8	Average number of students per computer with Internet connection enrolled in non-tertiary education (no.)	student computer access

Annex 3 - Themes per SDG

SDG1 - NO POVERTY			SDG2 - ZERO HUNGER			SDG3 - GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING			SDG4 - QUALITY EDUCATION			SDG5 - GENDER EQUALITY			SDG6 - CLEAR WATER AND SANITATION		
target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)
1.1; 1.2	poverty	G; U	2.1	access to safe, nutritious and sufficient food (food security)	G; U	3.4	prevention and treatment of non-communicable diseases	G	4.1	quality primary and secondary education	G; L; U	5.1	female discrimination	G	6	wastewater treatment	L
1.2; 1.3	social aid	L; U	2.3; 2.1	agri-prosumerism	L; U	3.4	mental health and well-being promotion	G	4.1; 4.6	basic education	L	5.1	gender equality in education, employment and income	U	6.1	accessible, safe and affordable drinking water	G; L; U
1.2	poverty risk	U	2.1	access & dependency to food supply aid	U	3.4	physical state and life expectancy	U	4.2	pre-school education and childcare	G; L; U	5.2	violence/domestic violence against women	G; L; U	6.1	households access to water	L; U
1.3	substantial coverage of the poor and vulnerable	G	2.1	financial accessibility to food; local food, key food items; healthy food basket	U	3.4	food safety and healthy diet	U	4.3	adult education	G; L	5.3	elimination of harmful practices against women	G; U	6.1	consumption in sectors	U
1.3	sickness benefits for working-age population	L	2.1	geographic accessibility and connectivity to healthy food; adequate food storage	U	3.4	proper housing and sanitation	U	4.3	professional training	G	5.5	female political participation (in local authorities)	G; L; U	6.2; 6.b	access to sanitation and hygiene	G; U
1.3	unemployment benefits	L	2.2	end all forms of malnutrition	G; U	3.4	physical activity	U	4.3	double certificate courses	L	5.5	women leadership	U	6.2	households access to wastewater drainage	L
1.4	equal rights to economic resources	G	2.2	stunting and wasting in children	G	3.4	access to food	U	4.3	post-secondary education (and university)	U	5.5	women in decision-making	U	6.b	participatory water management	G
1.4	access to basic services	G	2.2	nutritional needs of adolescent girls, pregnant and lactating women and older persons	G	3.4	access to green spaces	U	4.4	development of professional skills for employability	G	5.6	access to sexual and reproductive health and re-productive rights	G; U			
1.4	access to property and ownership	G; U	2.2	household food basket	U	3.4	safe walking and cycling paths	U	4.4	access to internet	L	5.b	women empowerment through technology	G; U			
1.4	housing affordability	L; U	2.3; 2.4	small/local farming	G; L	3.5	substance abuse	G; U	4.4	youth enrollment	U						
1.4	access to inheritance	G	2.3	equal access to land for food production	G; U	3.6	traffic accidents	G; L; U	4.4	workforce & marketplace needs	U						
1.4	access to natural resources	G		access to productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities	G	3.6	sustainable urban mobility	U	4.4	role of businesses	U						
1.4	access to water supply	L	2.3	job creation from growth in the food system	U	3.6	accessible public transport	U	4.5	disparities in education (gender, vulnerability, disabilities)	G; U						
1.4	access to appropriate new technology	G	2.3	farmers' income	U	3.7	access to sexual and reproductive health care services	G; L; U	4.6	literacy and numeracy	G; U						
1.4	access to financial services, including microfinance	G	2.3	financial services to food enterprises	U	3.7	reproductive health education and information	G	4.7	education for sustainable development	G						
1.4	subsidies	U	2.3	training opportunities	U	3.8	access to health-care services	G; L; U	4.7	education for healthy and sustainable lifestyles	G; U						
1.4; 1.2	household financial situation	L; U	2.3	local market opportunities	U	3.8	access to safe, effective, quality and affordable essential medicines and vaccines	G	4.7	education for human rights	G						
1.5	resilience for poor and vulnerable	G; U	2.3	supply and value chains, procurement contracts	U	3.9	pollution and contamination	G	4.7	education for gender equality	G						
1.5	hazardous locations households	U	2.4	sustainable food production	G	3.9	respiratory disease mortality	L	4.7	promotion peace and non-violence	G						
1.5	populations exposed to food risk	U	2.4	local food production	U	3.9	health education on medical substances	L	4.7	promotion of global citizenship	G						
1.5	reduce vulnerability	U	2.4	resilient agricultural practices	G	3.9	air quality policies and actions	U	4.7	appreciation of cultural diversity	G						
1.b	pro-poor and gender-sensitive development strategies	G	2.4	climate change adaptation capacity	G	3.9	preventing non-communicable diseases	U	4.7	appreciation of culture's contribution to sustainable development	G						
1.b	investment in poverty eradication actions	G	2.4	land use	U	3.9	noise and light pollution	U	4.7	early environmental awareness	U						
			2.4	cities self-sufficiency	U	3.7; 3.2	birth rates	L; U	4.a	inclusive educational facilities	G						
			2.4	eco-practices	U	3.d	health risk reduction on global health risks	G	4.a	access to computers	L						
			2.4	eco-policies	U				4.a	existence and quality of facilities (buildings and material)	U						
			2.4	circular economy	U				4.a	integrated urban planning	U						
			2.4	"food print"	U				4.a	resource consumption (e.g. water, energy),	U						
			2.5	diversity of seeds, plants and animals (crop varieties)	G; U				4.a	green procurement practices	U						
			2.5	seed and plant banks	G				4.a	effective learning conditions	U						
			2.5	fair and equitable sharing of commons	G				4.a	public libraries	U						

SDG7 - AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY			SDG8 - DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH			SDG9 - INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE			SDG10 - REDUCED INEQUALITIES			SDG11 - SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES			SDG12 - RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION		
target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)
7.1	affordable energy	G; U	8	foreign visitors to museums	L	9	municipal environmental expenditure	L	10.2	social, economic and political inclusion of all (age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status)	G; U	11.1	safe and affordable housing	G; L; U	12.2	sustainable management of natural resources	G; U
7.1	reliable energy	U	8.2	economic productivity	G; U	9.1	sustainable and resilient infrastructure	G	10.2	territorial income distribution	L	11.1	slums upgrade/informal housing	G; U	12.2	sustainable consumption and production	U
7.1	modern energy services	U	8.2	technological innovation	G; U	9.1	affordable and equitable access to resilient infrastructure	G	10.3	equal opportunity and outcome	G	11.1	access to adequate housing/basic services	G; U	12.2	energy, buildings, food sector, forest, industry, water	U
7.a	access to clean energy research and technology	G	8.2	High-tech workforce	U	9.1	community participation	L	10.3	care and education	U	11.1	living space	U	12.3	food loss	G; U
7.a	energy efficiency	U	8.3	productive activities	G	9.1	regional collaboration	U	10.7	safe, regular and responsible migration and mobility of people	G	11.1	evictions & homeless people	U	12.4	waste management	G; U
			8.3	job creation	G	9.1	transport infrastructure	U				11.1	social housing & subsidies	U	12.5	recycling and reuse	G; L; U
			8.3	entrepreneurship/ business creation	G; U	9.1	public and soft mobility modes	U				11.2	sustainable transport systems	G; U	12.5	urban waste collection	L; U
			8.3	creativity and innovation	G	9.1	electric mobility	U				11.2	road safety/traffic accidents	G; U	12.5	landfills	L
			8.3	micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises	G	9.1	water infrastructure	U				11.2	inclusive and affordable transport	G; U	12.5	waste prevention & reduction	U
			8.3	Green jobs creation	U	9.1	phone infrastructure	U				11.2	infrastructure – public transport, pedestrian & bikes	G; U	12.5	waste recovery - food systems	U
			8.3	labour rights	U	9.1	internet infrastructure	U				11.2	private car	U	12.5	circular economy	U
			8.5	inclusive employment	G	9.1	food infrastructure	U				11.2	shared vehicles and commuting	U	12.6	sustainable companies	G
			8.5	decent work	G	9.3	financial services for small-scale enterprises	G				11.2	low-emission vehicles	U	12.8	access to information on resilience	G; U
			8.5	employment rate	L	9.3	access to financial services	U				11.2	mobility plan and traffic management	U	12.8	awareness level for sustainable development and lifestyles	U
			8.5	unemployment benefits	L	9.5	technological capabilities	U				11.2	seniors' needs	U	12.8	environmental awareness campaigns	U
			8.5	gender income disparity	L	9.5	smart city policy	U				11.3	inclusive and sustainable urbanization	G; U	12.8	children awareness on resilience	U
			8.5	salary	L	9.c	access to information and communications technology	G				11.3	participatory planning	G; U			
			8.5	type of employment (part-time, temporary, instability)	U	9.c	internet access	G; L				11.3	integrated planning and management	G; U			
			8.5	informal sector	U							11.3	artificialised territories	L			
			8.5	'working poor'	U							11.3	land use and urban sprawl	U			
			8.5	satisfaction	U							11.3	land recycling	U			
			8.5	disconnected youth	U							11.3	future development strategy	U			
			8.6	youth unemployment	G							11.3	demography	U			
			8.7; 8.6	eradicate forced labour/ slavery and human trafficking/ child labour	G; U							11.3	local budget	U			
			8.7	child soldiers	G							11.3	satisfaction	U			
			8.7	domestic financial institutions	U							11.3	cultural and natural heritage protection	G; L; U			
			8.8	safe and secure working environments	G							11.4	biodiversity protection	L			
			8.8	secure working for migrant workers	G							11.4	visitors to museums	L			
			8.8	disparities in employment and income	U							11.4	cultural heritage protection	L; U			
			8.8	protection regulations	U							11.4	living culture	U			
			8.8	sustainable tourism	G; U							11.4	recreation	U			
			8.9	tourism and job creation	G							11.5	protect the poor from economic disasters	G			
			8.9	promotion of local culture and products	G							11.5	burnt forest areas and firefighters	L			
			8.9	decouple environmental degradation from economic growth	U							11.5	human and economic impacts of disasters	U			
			8.10	access to banking and financial services (banks, ATMs)	G; L							11.5	vulnerability	U			
			8.10	unhealthy working conditions	U							11.5	response to emergencies	U			
												11.6	waste management/ urban waste collection	G; U; L			
												11.6	urban landfills	L			
												11.6	environmental impact of cities	U			
												11.6	air quality	U			
												11.6	noise exposure	U			
												11.7	safe, inclusive and accessible, green and public spaces	G; U			
												11.7	urban water	U			
												11.7	trees and green infrastructure	U			
												11.7	public spaces-perception	U			
												11.a	economic, social and environmental links	G			
												11.a	regional development planning	U			

SDG13 - CLIMATE ACTION			SDG14 - LIFE BELOW WATER			SDG15 - LIFE ON LAND			SDG16 - PEACE, JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS			SDG17 - PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS		
target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)	target(s)	theme(s)	source(s)
13.3	climate change mitigation and adaptation education and awareness raising	G; U				15.1	forests, wetlands, mountains and drylands	G; L	16.1	reduce violence	G; U	17.8	technology bank	G
13.3	human and institutional capacity on climate change	G; U				15.1	quality water bodies	L	16.1	crimes against society	L	17.8	science, technology and innovation capacity-building mechanism	G
13.3	environmental NGOs	L				15.1	freshwater ecosystems	U	16.1	crimes against individuals	L	17.8	student computer access	L
						15.6	fair and equitable natural commons resources	G	16.1	crimes against property	L; U			
						15.a	biodiversity and ecosystems conservation and sustainable use	G	16.1	crimes against women	U			
						15.a	financial resources for biodiversity and ecosystems	U	16.1	violence at school	U			
									16.1	safety perception	U			
									16.1	assistance programmes for victims of violence	U			
									16.1	response against crimes	U			
									16.1	response against fires	U			
									16.1	response against other emergencies	U			
									16.2	end child abuse	G; U			
									16.6	effective, accountable and transparent institutions	G; L; U			
									16.6	municipal debt	L			
									16.6	municipal transparency	L			
										responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making	G; U			
									16.7	abstention from voting in municipal elections	L; U			
									16.7	civil representation in decision-making	U			
									16.7	local autonomy / governance	U			
									16.9	legal identity	G			
									16.9	birth registration	G			
									16.10	public access to information	G; U			
									16.10	fundamental freedoms	G			
									16.10	gender income disparity	L			
									16.10	open data	U			

Referenced Sources

No	Indicator Set	Published by
G	Global Indicator Framework	UN Habitat(Annex of the 2030 Agenda, 2017)
L	ODS Local	ODS Local, (CNADS), OBSERVA, MARE, 2adapt) Source: https://odslocal.pt/lisboa?lang=EN&tabId=tab-indicators
U	ETC/ULS ¹ Report 1/2020	Maio, S. de, Kuhn, S., Esteve, J. F., & Prokop, G. (2020). <i>Indicators for European cities to assess and monitor the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)</i> . 1–222.

¹ The European Topic Centre on Urban, Land and Soil Systems (ETC-ULS) is an assisting research organ of the European Environment Agency (EEA))